

Improving Manual Reviews in Function-centered Engineering of Embedded Systems Using a Dedicated Review Model

– Supplemental Material –

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Contents

- 1. Online-Questionnaire including the Experiment Material for Experiment 3 (English)**
- 2. Online-Questionnaire including the Experiment Material for Experiments 1 and 2 (German)**
- 3. Proof-of-Concept Implementation of QVTo Model Transformations for Review Model Creation**

1. Online-Questionnaire including the Experiment Material for Experiments 3

FDvsRM → base

Page 01
Welcome

Welcome and thank you for your participation

Thank you for participating in this experiment regarding reviews of model-based specifications against stakeholder intentions.

Please consider the experiment will last approximately 20-30 minutes.

Please do not use the back button of your browser. It is important that you complete the experiment straightforward.

Page 02
Briefing

Review of model-based specifications

On each of the next 4 pages, you will find one model-based specification. The specification will be either
a) a functional design consisting of function network diagrams and state machines

--OR--

b) a set of message sequence charts.

Below each specification you will find natural language stakeholder intentions. Please review the depicted models and decide whether the stakeholder intention is displayed in the specification or not. For each stakeholder intention, please rate your confidence in your decision.

Please review the functional design of a lane keeping support (LKS) with respect to stakeholder intentions

PHP code

```
question('LK03', 'combine=LK04', 'gap=line');
```

question('LK03', 'combine=LK04', 'gap=line')

Are following stakeholder intentions represented in the displayed functional design?

Please decide whether you think so, or not. In addition, please rate your confidence in the decision you made.

LK03
LK04

	yes	no	very confident	very unconfident
The LKS shall determine whether an automated intervention is necessary or not, based on a video stream monitoring the lane and the steering angle.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
In addition, it must be verified that no interventions are conducted if the driver intends to exit the lane. Therefore, it shall be requested, whether the indicator is activated or not.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To determine the corrected steering angle, instead of the desired steering angle at the steering wheel the actual yaw rate shall be used. Yawrate can be requested from another system.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
In case only minor interventions are needed the LKS shall conduct a steering intervention to the steering wheel, for larger interventions braking shall be used.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The driver must be able to override automated steering interventions at any time. Therefore, a manual steering command must stop all active intervention (to the wheel and to the brakes).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
After an intervention was conducted the LKS shall resume monitoring for additional interventions.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
In case yawrate and desired steering angle at the steering wheel differ by more than 10° no intervention shall be conducted as this commonly stems from erroneous data.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please review the functional design of a door control unit (DCU) with respect to stakeholder intentions

PHP code

```
question('DC03', 'combine=DC04', 'gap=line');
```

question('DC03', 'combine=DC04', 'gap=line')

Are following stakeholder intentions represented in the displayed functional design?

Please decide whether you think so, or not. In addition, please rate your confidence in the decision you made.

DC03
DC04

	yes	no	very confident	very unconfident
The DCU shall detect intrusion attempts from misuse of interior controls and from misuse of the interlocks. In addition, destruction of the car's windows shall be taken into account.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
In case of misuse of the interior control the DCU shall verify that no passenger is inside the car.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
When an intrusion attempt is detected, the car shall engage acoustic and optical warning.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
In addition, the intrusion attempt shall be verified for a second time.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
If the first intrusion attempt stems from a destruction of the car's windows, then the DCU shall immediately initiate an emergency call.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To allow for emergency calls, the GPS System shall periodically inform the DCU about the current GPS Position.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
In case the engine is running, intrusion detection shall only be conducted if the car is standing and the doors are locked.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please review following set of message sequence charts for a lane keeping support (LKS) with respect to stakeholder intentions

PHP code

```
question('LK01', 'combine=LK02', 'gap=line');
```

question('LK01', 'combine=LK02', 'gap=line')

Are following stakeholder intentions represented in the displayed message sequence charts?

Please decide whether you think so, or not. In addition, please rate your confidence in the decision you made.

LK01
LK02

	yes	no	very confident	very unconfident
The LKS shall determine whether an automated intervention is necessary or not, based on a video stream monitoring the lane and the steering angle.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
In addition, it must be verified that no interventions are conducted if the driver intends to exit the lane. Therefore, it shall be requested, whether the indicator is activated or not.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To determine the corrected steering angle, instead of the desired steering angle at the steering wheel the actual yaw rate shall be used. Yawrate can be requested from another system.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
In case only minor interventions are needed the LKS shall conduct a steering intervention to the steering wheel, for larger interventions braking shall be used.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The driver must be able to override automated steering interventions at any time. Therefore, a manual steering command must stop all active intervention (to the wheel and to the brakes).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
After an intervention was conducted the LKS shall resume monitoring for additional interventions.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
In case yawrate and desired steering angle at the steering wheel differ by more than 10° no intervention shall be conducted as this commonly stems from erroneous data.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please review following set of message sequence charts for a door control unit (DCU) with respect to stakeholder intentions

PHP code

```
question('DC01', 'combine=DC02', 'gap=line');
```

question('DC01', 'combine=DC02', 'gap=line')

Are following stakeholder intentions represented in the displayed message sequence charts?

Please decide whether you think so, or not. In addition, please rate your confidence in the decision you made.

DC01
DC02

	yes	no	very confident	very unconfident
The DCU shall detect intrusion attempts from misuse of interior controls and from misuse of the interlocks. In addition, destruction of the car's windows shall be taken into account.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
In case of misuse of the interior control the DCU shall verify that no passenger is inside the car.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
When an intrusion attempt is detected, the car shall engage acoustic and optical warning.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
In addition, the intrusion attempt shall be verified for a second time.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
If the first intrusion attempt stems from a destruction of the car's windows, then the DCU shall immediately initiate an emergency call.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To allow for emergency calls, the GPS System shall periodically inform the DCU about the current GPS Position.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
In case the engine is running, intrusion detection shall only be conducted if the car is standing and the doors are locked.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please rate your comfort using a review model (reviewing the message sequence charts) instead of the functional design

During your review you partly reviewed the original specification of the **functional design** (function networks and state machines) or a dedicated **review model** (message sequence charts) that displayed the same information as specified in the functional design. Within the next questions we want to elicit your opinion on reviewing the review model instead of reviewing the original functional design.

PQ02

To which extent do you agree with following statements?

Experience and Personal Data

Please rate your experience with following development activities and model notations

PQ01

	very experienced				very inexperienced
Model-based documentation of requirements	<input type="radio"/>				
Development of embedded systems	<input type="radio"/>				
Message Sequence Charts	<input type="radio"/>				
Models for documenting the functional design	<input type="radio"/>				
Finite State Machines	<input type="radio"/>				
Conducting reviews of model-based specifications	<input type="radio"/>				

Please support us with some personal data, which will be analyzed anonymous

PD01

Age years

Gender

Highest educational degree (e.g. Abitur, Bachelor, etc.)

Subject of highest educational degree (e.g. WiInf, AI-SE, etc.)

Target educational degree

Subject of target educational degree

Semesters studied in current degree program semesters

Anticipated end of study

Thank you for completing this questionnaire!

We would like to thank you very much for helping us.

Your answers were transmitted, you may close the browser window or tab now.

Marian Daun, Universität Duisburg-Essen – 2018

2. Online-Questionnaire including the Experiment Material for Experiments 1 and 2

Herzlich Willkommen! Vielen Dank für Ihre Teilnahme!

Vielen Dank für Ihre Teilnahme an diesem Experiment. Das Experiment beschäftigt sich mit dem manuellen Review modellbasierter Spezifikationen gegen Stakeholder Intentions.

Das Experiment wird etwa 30-40min dauern. Bitte planen Sie für diese Zeit keine weiteren Tätigkeiten ein, da wir auch die Bearbeitungszeit messen werden.

Bitte benutzen Sie nicht den Zurück-Button ihres Browsers, da es für uns wichtig ist, dass Sie die einzelnen Fragen der Reihe nach, ohne Rückschritte, beantworten.

Review von modellbasierten Spezifikationen

Auf den nächsten beiden Seiten werden Sie Modelle finden, die wir Sie bitten möchten gegen textuelle Aussagen zu überprüfen. Im Detail finden Sie

- a) zwei original Spezifikationen der Behavioral Requirements und des Functional Design
- b) ein Review Model, dass die Informationen aus den Behavioral Requirements und dem Functional Design in einem Modell darstellt.

Unter den Spezifikationen finden Sie textuelle Stakeholder Intentions. Wir möchten Sie bitten, die dargestellten Modelle zu reviewen und zu entscheiden, ob die textuellen Aussagen in den Spezifikationen dargestellt sind. Bitte geben Sie auch Ihr Selbstvertrauen (Confidence) bei jeder einzelnen Entscheidung an.

Nachfolgend ist sind zwei Spezifikationen gegeben: Die Behavioral Requirements und das Functional Design eines Kollisionsvermeidungssystems (PCAS). Bitte führen Sie jetzt einen Review dieser Spezifikationen durch.

Behavioral Requirements

Functional Design

In welcher Spezifikation sind die nachfolgenden Stakeholder Intentions dargestellt?

Sie sehen zwei Spezifikationen (die Behavioral Requirements BR und das Functional Design FD). Bitte entscheiden Sie, ob die nachfolgenden Stakeholder Intentions in den Behavioral Requirements (BR), im Functional Design (FD), in beiden Spezifikationen oder in keiner der Spezifikationen enthalten sind.

Bitte geben Sie auch Ihre „Confidence“ an. D.h. Ihre eigene Zuversicht, dass die von Ihnen getroffene Entscheidung richtig ist.

	Nur in BR	Nur in FD	In beiden	In keiner	very confident	very unconfident
Das PCAS soll automatisch durch den Autopiloten oder manuell durch den Piloten aktiviert werden. In jedem Fall meldet sich das PCAS beim Sekundärradar an und informiert den Piloten darüber, dass das PCAS aktiv ist.	<input type="radio"/>					
Nach der Aktivierung überwacht das PCAS den Flugraum und verhindert Kollisionen. Dies geschieht solange bis, das PCAS deaktiviert wird.	<input type="radio"/>					
Zur Überwachung des Luftraums sendet das Sekundärradar die eigene Flugzeugidentifikation an andere Flugzeuge.	<input type="radio"/>					
Während das PCAS aktiv ist, überprüft es immer wieder die Funktionsfähigkeit des Sekundärradars, indem eine Testanfrage versendet und eine Testantwort erhalten wird.	<input type="radio"/>					
Empfängt das Sekundärradar eine fremde Flugzeugidentifikation, so leitet es diese an das PCAS weiter.	<input type="radio"/>					
Der Austausch beider Flugzeugidentifikationen kann hierbei in beliebiger Reihenfolge passieren.	<input type="radio"/>					
Um die eigene Flugkarte zu erhalten, erfragt das PCAS beim Autopiloten in regelmäßigen Abständen den aktuellen Flugplan	<input type="radio"/>					
Würde ein Flugzeug in Radarreichweite erkannt, so tauscht das PCAS mit diesem über das Sekundärradar die Flugkarten beider Flugzeuge aus.	<input type="radio"/>					
Erkennt das PCAS anhand der beiden Karten eine bevorstehende Kollision, so informiert es zunächst den Piloten.	<input type="radio"/>					
Nach der Kollisionserkennung wird geprüft, welches Flugzeug ausweichpflichtig ist. Der Pilot wird in jedem Fall über das Ergebnis informiert.	<input type="radio"/>					
Ist das eigene Flugzeug ausweichpflichtig, so wird ein neuer Flugplan errechnet und an den Autopiloten gegeben.	<input type="radio"/>					
Außerdem wird die neue Flugkarte an das andere Flugzeug übermittelt	<input type="radio"/>					

Nachfolgend ist ein spezielles Review Modell für ein Kollisionsvermeidungssystem (PCAS) gegeben. Dieses Modell stellt Informationen die nur im Functional Design spezifiziert wurden rot dar, Informationen die nur in den Behavioral Requirements spezifiziert wurden blau. Alle anderen dargestellten Informationen sind in beiden Spezifikationen (Behavioral Requirements und Functional Design) vorhanden. Bitte führen Sie jetzt einen Review dieses Review Modells durch.

In welcher Spezifikation sind die nachfolgenden Stakeholder Intentions dargestellt?

Sie sehen ein Review Modell, das die Inhalte zweier Spezifikationen in einem Modell darstellt. Bitte entscheiden Sie, ob die nachfolgenden Stakeholder Intentions in den Behavioral Requirements (BR), im Functional Design (FD), in beiden Spezifikationen oder in keiner der Spezifikationen enthalten sind.

Bitte geben Sie auch Ihre „Confidence“ an. D.h. Ihre eigene Zuversicht, dass die von Ihnen getroffene Entscheidung richtig ist.

	Nur in BR	Nur in FD	In beiden	In keiner	Confidence
Das PCAS soll automatisch durch den Autopiloten oder manuell durch den Piloten aktiviert werden. In jedem Fall meldet sich das PCAS beim Sekundärradar an und informiert den Piloten darüber, dass das PCAS aktiv ist.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	
Nach der Aktivierung überwacht das PCAS den Flugraum und verhindert Kollisionen. Dies geschieht solange bis, das PCAS deaktiviert wird.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	
Zur Überwachung des Luftraums sendet das Sekundärradar die eigene Flugzeugidentifikation an andere Flugzeuge.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	
Während das PCAS aktiv ist, überprüft es immer wieder die Funktionsfähigkeit des Sekundärradars, indem eine Testanfrage versendet und eine Testantwort erhalten wird.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	
Empfängt das Sekundärradar eine fremde Flugzeugidentifikation, so leitet es diese an das PCAS weiter.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	
Der Austausch beider Flugzeugidentifikationen kann hierbei in beliebiger Reihenfolge passieren.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	
Um die eigene Flugkarte zu erhalten, erfragt das PCAS beim Autopiloten in regelmäßigen Abständen den aktuellen Flugplan	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	
Wurde ein Flugzeug in Radarreichweite erkannt, so tauscht das PCAS mit diesem über das Sekundärradar die Flugkarten beider Flugzeuge aus.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	
Erkennt das PCAS anhand der beiden Karten eine bevorstehende Kollision, so informiert es zunächst den Piloten.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	
Nach der Kollisionserkennung wird geprüft, welches Flugzeug ausweichpflichtig ist. Der Pilot wird in jedem Fall über das Ergebnis informiert.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	
Ist das eigene Flugzeug ausweichpflichtig, so wird ein neuer Flugplan errechnet und an den Autopiloten gegeben.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	
Außerdem wird die neue Flugkarte an das andere Flugzeug übermittelt	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	

Bitte bewerten Sie Ihr Empfinden bei den beiden von Ihnen durchgeführten Reviews

Welches Modell (das Review Modell oder die originalen Spezifikationen) würden Sie bevorzugen?

PQ02

	das Review Modell		die Originalen Spezifikationen	
Meine Performance im manuellen Review wird am besten durch folgendes Modell unterstützt	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Meine Produktivität im manuellen Review wird am besten durch folgendes Modell unterstützt	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Ich bin am effektivsten wenn ich folgendes Modell für den manuellen Review nutze	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Ich finde folgendes Modell am nützlichsten, um einen manuellen Review durchzuführen	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Für mich ist die Benutzung folgendes Modells im manuellen Review am einfachsten und verständlichsten	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Der Review folgendes Modells ist für mich mit den wenigsten mentalen Anstrengungen verbunden	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
In manuellen Reviews finde ich folgendes Modell einfacher zu nutzen	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Wenn es niemanden gäbe, der mir eine Einführung geben könnte, würde ich folgendes Modell für den manuellen Review bevorzugen	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Wenn es jemanden gäbe, der mir zu Beginn zeigen würde, wie ich das Modell nutzen kann, würde ich folgendes Modell für den manuellen Review bevorzugen	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Wenn ich schon vorher vergleichbare Modelltypen genutzt hätte, würde ich den manuellen Review folgendes Modells bevorzugen	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Erfahrung und Biografische Angaben

Bitte schätzen Sie Ihre Erfahrung mit den nachfolgenden Entwicklungsaktivitäten und Notationsformen ein.

PQ01

	sehr erfahren				sehr unerfahren
Modellbasiertes Requirements Engineering	<input type="radio"/>				
Entwicklung eingebetteter Systeme	<input type="radio"/>				
Message Sequence Charts	<input type="radio"/>				

Bitte unterstützen Sie uns mit einigen biografischen Informationen

PD01

Alter Jahre

Geschlecht

Höchster bisheriger
Bildungsabschluss
(falls zutreffend mit
Studiengangname)

Aktuelle
Haupttätigkeit

PD04

PD05

PD06

Bitte unterstützen Sie uns noch mit einigen weiteren biografischen Daten. Die Daten werden selbstverständlich vollständig anonym ausgewertet.

PHP code

```
if (value('PD06') == 2) {  
    question('PD02');  
}  
else {  
    question('PD03');  
}
```

question('PD02')

PD02

Angestrebter
Studienabschluss

Studiengang

seit x Semestern in
diesem Studiengang
eingeschrieben Semester

Vorraussichtliches
Studienende

question('PD03')

PD03

Berufsbezeichnung

In aktueller Stellung
seit Jahre

Berufserfahrung in
Jahren Jahre

Thank you for completing this questionnaire!

We would like to thank you very much for helping us.

Your answers were transmitted, you may close the browser window or tab now.

3. Proof-of-Concept Implementation of QVTo Model Transformations for Review Model Creation

Creation of intermediate interface automata based on the behavioral requirements

```
modeltype UML uses 'http://www.eclipse.org/uml2/5.0.0/UML';

transformation BMSCtoIA(in bmsc:UML, in profile:UML, out ia:UML);

    property systemlifeline:Lifeline =null;
    property nameofsystemlifeline:String=null;
    property sourcestate:Pseudostate=null;
    property model : UML::Model = null;
    property regions:Region= null;

main()
{
    log("Start Transformation");
    model := object Model { name :='model' };
    bmsc.rootObjects().allSubobjectsOfType(UML);
    var stereo:= profile.objects()[Stereotype] ->any(name='IAProfile:'+ name);
    model.applyProfile(profile.objectsOfType(Profile)![name='IAProfile']);

    model.packagedElement +=map CreateStateMachine();
    profile.objectsOfType(Stereotype) -> StereotypeToState();
    profile.objectsOfType(Stereotype) -> StereotypeToTransition();

    var controlflows:=bmsc.objectsOfType(ControlFlow);
    var counter:=0;
    controlflows->forEach(cf)
    {
        if cf.sourceisInteraction()==true then
        {
            if cf.targetisInteraction()==true then
            {
                counter:=counter+1;
                map
                createHMSTransition(cf.source.name,cf.target.name,counter)
            }endif;
        }endif;
    };

    epsilonTransition();
    deleteEpsilonAndEndStates();

    var transition:=ia.objectsOfType(Transition);
    transition->forEach(t)
    {
        regions.transition+=t;
    };
    profile.objectsOfType(Stereotype) -> StereotypeToTransition();
    var states:=ia.objectsOfType(Pseudostate);
    states->forEach(s)
    {
        if s.name.substringAfter(";")=null then s.name:="" else s.name:=
        s.name.substringAfter(";") endif;
    };

    states->forEach(s)
    {
        if s.isStereotypedByState("IAProfile::Start") then if s.incoming-
        >notEmpty() then s.unapplyStereotype(getStereotype("Start")) endif
        endif;
    };
};
```

```

        if s.isStereotypedbyState("IAPprofile::End") then if s.outgoing-
        >notEmpty() then s.unapplyStereotype(getStereotype("End")) endif
        endif;
    };
    log("End Transformation");
}

mapping CreateStateMachine():StateMachine
{
    name:="StateMachine";
    var regionid:=map regiontoState();
    region:=regionid;
    regions:=regionid;
}

mapping regiontoState():Region
{
    name:="Region1";
    var interactions:=bmsc.objectsOfType(Interaction);
    var messages:=bmsc.objectsOfType(MessageOccurrenceSpecification);

    interactions->forEach(i)
    {
        var state:Pseudostate:= object Pseudostate{name:=""+i.name;
        kind:=PseudostateKind::junction;};
        sourcestate:=state;
        systemlifeline:=i.getLifelineID();
        nameofsystemlifeline:=systemlifeline.name;
        messages->forEach(m)
        {
            if i.message->includes(m.message) then
            {
                var nameofmessage:=m.name;
                nameofmessage:=nameofmessage.substringBefore("Recv");
                if nameofmessage=null then
                {
                    log("aktuelle Nachricht von Send: " +
m.message.name);

                    var state1:Pseudostate:= object Pseudostate{name:=
m.message.name+i.name;
                    kind:=PseudostateKind::junction;};
                    var transition:Transition:= object
                    Transition{name:= m.message.name;
                    source:=sourcestate; target:=state1;};
                    sourcestate:=state1;
                } endif;
            } endif;
        }
    };
    var states:=ia.objectsOfType(Pseudostate);
    states->forEach(s)
    {
        subvertex+=s;
    };
    var transitions:=ia.objectsOfType(Transition);
    transitions->forEach(t)
    {
        transition+=t;
    };
}

mapping Stereotype::StereoTypetoState()
{
    var state := ia.objectsOfType(Pseudostate);
    state->forEach(s)
    {
        if self.name="Start" then if s.startstate()==true then
s.applyStereotype(self) endif endif;
        if self.name="End" then if s.endstate()==true then
s.applyStereotype(self) endif endif;
    }
}

```

```

};
}

helper Stereotype::StereoTypetoTransition()
{
    var transition:=ia.objectsOfType(Transition);
    transition->forEach(t)
    {
        if self.name="Input" then if t.inputoroutput()=true then
{t.applyStereotype(self)} endif endif;
        if self.name="Output" then if t.inputoroutput()=false then
{t.applyStereotype(self)} endif endif;
    };
}

mapping createHMSTransition (sourceIA:String,targetIA:String,
count:Integer):Transition
{
    name:="Epsilon" + count.toString();
    source:=getfinalstate(sourceIA);
    target:=getstartstate(targetIA);
}

helper getNameofaddressat(str : String) : String
{
    var addressat: String;
    var life := bmsc.objectsOfType(Lifeline);
    life->forEach(l)
    {
        var mos:= bmsc.objectsOfType(MessageOccurrenceSpecification);
        mos->forEach(m)
        {
            if m.name = str then if m.covered->includes(l) then addressat:=
l.name endif endif;
        };
    };
    return addressat;
}

helper Interaction::getLifelineID():Lifeline
{
    var lifelines:=bmsc.objectsOfType(Lifeline);
    lifelines->forEach(l)
    {
        if self.lifeline->includes(l) then
            if l.isStereotypedBy("bmscProfile::System") then return l
            endif
        endif;
    };
    return null;
}

helper Lifeline::isStereotypedBy ( str : String ) : Boolean
{
    var st : Stereotype := null;
    st := self.getAppliedStereotype( str );
    return if ( self.isStereotypeApplied(st) ) then true else false endif;
}

helper Pseudostate::startstate():Boolean
{
    var transitions:=ia.objectsOfType(Transition);
    var startstate:Boolean:=true;
    transitions->forEach(t)
    {
        if t.target=self then startstate:=false endif;
    };
    return startstate;
}

```

```

helper Pseudostate::endstate():Boolean
{
    var transitions:=ia.objectsOfType(Transition);
    var endstate:Boolean:=true;
    transitions->forEach(t)
    {
        if t.source=self then endstate:=false endif;
    };
    return endstate;
}

helper Transition::inputoroutput():Boolean
{
    var input:Boolean:=false;
    var msg:=bmsc.objectsOfType(Message);
    msg->forEach(m)
    {
        if self.name=m.name then if
            IsSystemLifeline(getNameofaddressat(m.receiveEvent.name)) then
                input:=true else input:=false endif endif;
    };
    return input;
}

helper ControlFlow::sourceisInteraction():Boolean
{
    var isIA:Boolean:=false;
    var Interactions:=bmsc.objectsOfType(Interaction);
    Interactions->forEach(i)
    {
        if self.source.name=i.name then isIA:=true endif;
    };
    return isIA;
}

helper ControlFlow::targetisInteraction():Boolean
{
    var isIA:Boolean:=false;
    var Interactions:=bmsc.objectsOfType(Interaction);
    Interactions->forEach(i)
    {
        if self.target.name=i.name then isIA:=true endif;
    };
    return isIA;
}

helper getfinalstate(str:String):Pseudostate
{
    var states:=ia.objectsOfType(Pseudostate);
    states->forEach(s)
    {
        var nameafter:= s.name.substringAfter(str);
        if nameafter="" then
            if s.isStereotypedbyState("IAProfile::End")=true then
                return s
            endif
        endif;
    };
    return null;
}

helper getstartstate(str:String):Pseudostate
{
    var states:=ia.objectsOfType(Pseudostate);
    states->forEach(s)
    {
        var nameafter:= s.name.substringAfter(str);
        if nameafter="" then
            if s.isStereotypedbyState("IAProfile::Start")=true then
                return s
            endif
        endif;
    };
    return null;
}

```

```

        endif
    endif;
};

return null;
}

helper Pseudostate::isStereotypedbyState ( str : String ) : Boolean
{
    var st : Stereotype := null;
    st := self.getAppliedStereotype( str );
    return if ( self.isStereotypeApplied(st) ) then true else false endif;
}

helper epsilontransition()
{
    var messages:=ia.objectsOfType(Transition);
    messages->forEach(me)
    {
        if me.name.substringBefore("Epsilon")="" then
        {
            messages->forEach(m)
            {
                if me.source=m.target then
                {
                    var message:Transition:= object
Transition{name:=m.name; source:=m.source; target:=me.target;};
                    } endif;
                }
            } endif;
        }
    }
}

helper deleteepsilonandendstates()
{
    var messages:=ia.objectsOfType(Transition);
    messages->forEach(me)
    {
        if me.name.substringBefore("Epsilon")="" then
        {
            messages->forEach(m)
            {
                if me.source=m.target then
                {
                    ia.removeElement(m);
                } endif;
            };
            ia.removeElement(me.source);
            ia.removeElement(me);
        } endif;
    }
}

helper getStereotype(str:String):Stereotype
{
    var stereos:=profile.objectsOfType(Stereotype);
    stereos->forEach(s)
    {
        if s.name=str then {return s; break;} endif;
    };
    return null;
}

helper IsSystemLifeline(str:String):Boolean
{
    var issystem:Boolean:=false;
    var lifeline:=bmsc.objectsOfType(Lifeline);
    lifeline->forEach(l)
    {

```

```

        if l.name=str then if l.isStereotypedBy("bmscProfile::System") then
        {issystem:=true; break;} endif endif;
    };
    return issystem;
}

helper Transition::isStereotyped ( str : String ) : Boolean
{
    var st : Stereotype := null;
    st := self.getAppliedStereotype( str );
    return if ( self.isStereotypeApplied(st) ) then true else false endif;
}

```

Composition of interface automata

```

modeltype UML uses 'http://www.eclipse.org/uml2/5.0.0/UML';
modeltype ECORE uses "http://www.eclipse.org/emf/2002/Ecore";

transformation compositionofIA(in ia1:UML,in ia2:UML,in profile:UML,out pa:UML);

    property model : UML::Model = null;
    property samemessage:List(String)=null;
    property ialb:List(String)=null;
    property ia1a:List(String)=null;
    property ia2b:List(String)=null;
    property ia2a:List(String)=null;
    property ia1causalStates:Set(String)=Set{};
    property ia2causalStates:Set(String)=Set{};
    property removeStates:Set(Vertex)=Set{};

main() {
    log("Start Transformation");

    model := object Model { name :='model' };
    model.applyProfile(profile.objectsOfType(Profile)![name='IAProfile']);
    model.packageElement +=map CreateStateMachine();

    samemessage->forEach(sm)
    {
        pa.objectsOfType(Transition)->forEach(t)
        {
            if t.name=sm then if t.source.countoutgoingtransition() then
            removeunreachableStates(t.source, t)endif endif;
        }
    };
    profile.objectsOfType(Stereotype) ->map StereotypeToState();
    profile.objectsOfType(Stereotype) ->map StereotypeToTransition();
    log("Transformation Finished");
}

mapping CreateStateMachine():StateMachine
{
    name:="StateMachine";
    var reg:=map regionToState();
    region:=reg;
}

mapping regionToState():Region
{
    name:="Region1";
    getsamemessage();
    if samemessage->isEmpty() then {map createProducts(); map
        createMessages(); log("no internal messages.")} else
    }endif;
    if samemessage!=null then {FindreachableStates(); map createMessages(); }
endif;

    var trans:=pa.objectsOfType(Transition);
    trans->forEach(t)

```

```

    {
        transition+=t
    };
    var states:=pa.objectsOfType(Pseudostate);
    states->forEach(s)
    {
        subvertex+=s
    };
}

mapping createProducts()
{
    var iface1:=ia1.objectsOfType(Pseudostate);
    var iface2:=ia2.objectsOfType(Pseudostate);
    iface1->forEach(i1)
    {
        iface2->forEach(i2)
        {
            var State:Pseudostate:= object Pseudostate{name:=i1.toString() +
                "," + i2.toString(); kind:=PseudostateKind::junction;};
        };
    };
}

mapping createMessages()
{
    var iface1:=ia1.objectsOfType(Transition);
    var iface2:=ia2.objectsOfType(Transition);
    var states:=pa.objectsOfType(Pseudostate);
    states->forEach(s1)
    {
        iface1->forEach(i1)
        {
            var help:=s1.name;
            var help1:=help.substringAfter(i1.source.toString()+",");

            if
s1.name.toString().substringBefore(",org")=i1.source.toString() then
                states->forEach(s2)
                {
                    var help2:=s2.name.toString();
                    var
help3:=help2.substringAfter(i1.target.toString()+",");
                    if help1=help3 then
                        { if samemessage->includes(i1.name)=false then map
                            createTransition(s1,s2,i1.name) endif}
                        endif;
                    } endif;
                };
            iface2->forEach(i2)
            {
                var help:=s1.name;
                var help1:=help.substringBefore(", "+i2.source.toString());
                if
s1.name.toString().substringAfter("junction,")=i2.source.toStri
ng() then
                    states->forEach(s2)
                    {
                        var help2:=s2.name;
                        var
help3:=help2.substringBefore(", "+i2.target.toString());
                        if help1=help3 then
                            { if samemessage->includes(i2.name)=false then map
                                createTransition(s1,s2,i2.name) endif}
                            endif;
                        }endif;
                    };
                };
            };
        };
    };
}

```

```

    }
}

mapping createTransition(s1:Pseudostate,s2:Pseudostate, n:String)
{
    var message:Transition:=object Transition
    {
        name:=n;
        source:=s1;
        target:=s2;
    }
}

helper getsamemessage()
{
    var iface1:=ia1.objectsOfType(Transition);
    var iface2:=ia2.objectsOfType(Transition);

    iface1->forEach(i1)
    {
        iface2->forEach(i2)
        {
            if i1.name=i2.name then samemessage+=i1.name endif;
        };
    };
    samemessage->forEach(sm) {log("Internal Messages: "+sm)};
}

helper getcausalstates()
{
    var st1:=ia1.objectsOfType(Pseudostate);
    var st2:=ia2.objectsOfType(Pseudostate);
    var listStartcausal:List(String):=List{};
    var listEndcausal:List(String):=List{};
    var listStartcausal2:List(String):=List{};
    var listEndcausal2:List(String):=List{};
    var tr1:=ia1.objectsOfType(Transition);
    var tr2:=ia2.objectsOfType(Transition);
    st1->forEach(s1)
    {
        var countersource:=0;
        var countertarget:=0;
        tr1->forEach(t1)
        {
            if t1.source=s1 then countersource:=countersource+ 1 endif;
            if t1.target=s1 then countertarget:=countertarget+ 1 endif;
            if countersource>1 then listStartcausal+= s1.toString() endif;
            if countertarget>1 then listEndcausal+= s1.toString() endif;
        };
    };
    st1->forEach(s1)
    {
        tr1->forEach(t1)
        {
            if listStartcausal->includes(t1.source.toString())=true then if
            ialcausalStates->includes(t1.target.toString())=false then
            ialcausalStates+=t1.target.toString() endif endif;
            if ialcausalStates->includes(t1.source.toString())=true then if
            ialcausalStates->includes(t1.target.toString())=false
            then if listEndcausal->includes(t1.target.toString())=true then
            ialcausalStates+=t1.target.toString() endif endif endif;
        };
    };
    st2->forEach(s2)
    {
        var countersource:=0;
        var countertarget:=0;
        tr2->forEach(t2)
        {

```

```

        if t2.source=s2 then countersource:=countersource+ 1 endif;
        if t2.target=s2 then countertarget:=countertarget+ 1 endif;
        if countersource>1 then listStartcausal2+= s2.toString() endif;
        if countertarget>1 then listEndcausal2+= s2.toString() endif;
    };
};
st2->forEach(s2)
{
    tr2->forEach(t2)
    {
        if listStartcausal2->includes(t2.source.toString())=true then if
        ia2causalStates->includes(t2.target.toString())=false then
        ia2causalStates+=t2.target.toString() endif endif;
        if ia2causalStates->includes(t2.source.toString())=true then if
        ia2causalStates->includes(t2.target.toString())=false
        then if listEndcausal2->includes(t2.target.toString())=true then
        ia2causalStates+=t2.target.toString() endif endif endif;
    };
};
}

helper FindreachableStates ()
{
    checkdoublemessages ();
    var helperState:Pseudostate;
    var counter:=0;
    var previous:String="";
    samemessage->forEach(sm)
    {
        sm.fillStates(sm.nextmessage(),counter, previous);

        log(sm);
        ialb->forEach(i){log("ialb: " + i)};
        ia2b->forEach(i){log("ia2b: " + i)};
        iala->forEach(i){log("iala: " + i)};
        ia2a->forEach(i){log("ia2a: " + i)};
        var countstates:=0;

        if counter=0 then
        {
            if getcount("ialb")!=0 and getcount("ia2b")!=0 then
            {
                ialb->forEach(b1)
                {
                    ia2b->forEach(b2)
                    {
                        var State1:Pseudostate:= object Pseudostate{
                            name:=b1+", "+b2;kind:=PseudostateKind::junction;};
                        helperState:=State1;
                        countstates:=countstates+1;
                        log("Statescounter: "+
                            countstates.toString());
                    };
                };
            }
            else if getcount("ialb")!=0 and getcount("ia2b")=0 then
            {
                ialb->forEach(b1)
                {
                    var State1:Pseudostate:= object Pseudostate{
                            name:=b1 + ",";
                            kind:=PseudostateKind::junction;};
                        helperState:=State1;
                    };
                };
            }
            else if getcount("ialb")=0 and getcount("ia2b")!=0 then
            {
                ia2b->forEach(b2)

```

```

        {
            var State1:Pseudostate:= object
            Pseudostate{name:=", "+b2;
            kind:=PseudostateKind::junction;};
            helperState:=State1;
        };
    }
endif endif endif;
var State2:Pseudostate:= object
Pseudostate{name:=sm.getPseudoState("1") + "," +
sm.getPseudoState("2"); kind:=PseudostateKind::junction;};
var transition:Transition:=object Transition
{
    name:=sm;
    source:=helperState;
    target:=State2;
};
helperState:=State2;
if (getcount("iala")!=0 and getcount("ia2a")!=0) and
(getcount("iala")!=1 and getcount("ia2a")!=1) then
{
    iala->forEach(a1)
    {
        ia2a->forEach(a2)
        {
            var State3:Pseudostate:= object
            Pseudostate{name:=a1 + "," +
            a2;kind:=PseudostateKind::junction;};
            helperState:=State3
        };
    };
}
else if getcount("iala")!=0 and getcount("ia2a")=0 then
{
    iala->forEach(a1)
    {
        helperState:=a1.map
        helpercreateState(sm.getPseudoState("2"), true);
    }
}
else if getcount("iala")=0 and getcount("ia2a")!=0 then
{
    ia2a->forEach(a2)
    {
        helperState:=a2.map
        helpercreateState(sm.getPseudoState("1"), false);
    }
}
endif endif endif;
}
else
{
    var State2:Pseudostate:= object
    Pseudostate{name:=sm.getPseudoState("1") + "," +
    sm.getPseudoState("2");kind:=PseudostateKind::junction;
    log(sm + " " +sm.getPseudoState("1"));
    log(sm + " " +sm.getPseudoState("2"))};
    var transition:Transition:=object Transition
    {
        name:=sm;
        source:=helperState;
        target:=State2;
    };
    helperState:=State2;
    if (getcount("iala")!=0 and getcount("ia2a")!=0) and
    (getcount("iala")!=1 and getcount("ia2a")!=1) then
    {
        iala->forEach(a1)
        {

```

```

        ia2a->forEach(a2)
        {
            var State3:Pseudostate:= object Pseudostate{
                name:=a1+", "+a2;kind:=PseudostateKind::junction;};
            helperState:=State3;
        };
    }
    else if getcount("iala")!=0 and getcount("ia2a")==0 then
    {
        iala->forEach(a1)
        {
            helperState:=a1.map
            helpercreateState(sm.getPseudoState("2"),true)
        }
        else if getcount("iala")==0 and getcount("ia2a")!=0 then
        {
            ia2a->forEach(a2)
            {
                helperState:=a2.map
                helpercreateState(sm.getPseudoState("1"),false);
            };
        } endif endif endif;
    }endif;
    counter:=counter+1;
    previous:=sm;
};
}

mapping String::helpercreateState(str:String, first:Boolean):Pseudostate
{
    if first=true then name:=self+", "+str else name:=str+", " +self endif;
    kind:=PseudostateKind::junction;
}

helper String::fillStates(str:String, count:Integer, previousMessage:String)
{
    iala:=null;
    ia2a:=null;
    ialb:=null;
    ia2b:=null;
    var messagefind:=false;
    var nextmessage:=false;
    if count=0 then
    {
        var startstate:=getStartState(true);
        var iface1:=ial.objectsOfType(Transition);
        iface1->forEach(i1)
        {
            if i1.source=startstate then
            {
                if i1.name=self then { messagefind:=true;
                ialb+=i1.source.toString(); }endif;
                if messagefind=false then {ialb+=startstate.toString();}
endif;

                if i1.name=str then {nextmessage:=true; } endif;
                if messagefind=true then if nextmessage=false then
                iala+=i1.target.toString() endif endif;
                var
targetstate:Pseudostate=i1.target.getPseudostate(true);
                if nextmessage=false then
                {self.getrecursiveStates(messagefind, nextmessage, str,
                targetstate,true,count);} endif;
            } endif;
        };
        messagefind:=false;
    }
}

```

```

nextmessage:=false;
var startstate2:=getStartState(false);
var iface2:=ia2.objectsOfType(Transition);
iface2->forEach(i2)
{
    if i2.source=startstate2 then
    {
        if i2.name=self then { messagefind:=true;
        ia2b+=i2.source.toString()}endif;
        if messagefind=false then {ia2b+=startstate2.toString()}
endif;

        if i2.name=str then {nextmessage:=true; } endif;
        if messagefind=true then if nextmessage=false then
        ia2a+=i2.target.toString() endif endif;
        var
targetstate:Pseudostate=i2.target.getPseudostate(false);
        if nextmessage=false then
        {self.getrecursiveStates(messagefind, nextmessage, str,
        targetstate,false,count);} endif;
    } endif;
}

}
else
{

var iface1:=ia1.objectsOfType(Transition);
iface1->forEach(i1)
{
    if self=i1.name then
    {
        if messagefind=true then if nextmessage=false then if
        ia1a->includes(i1.target.toString())=false then
        ia1a+=i1.target.toString() endif endif endif;
        if i1.name=self then messagefind:=true endif;
        if i1.name=str then nextmessage:=true endif;
        var
targetstate:Pseudostate=i1.target.getPseudostate(true);
        if nextmessage=false then
        {self.getrecursiveStates(messagefind, nextmessage, str, targetstate,true, count);}
endif;

    }endif;
};
messagefind:=false;
nextmessage:=false;
var iface2:=ia2.objectsOfType(Transition);
iface2->forEach(i2)
{
    if self=i2.name then
    {
        if messagefind=true then if nextmessage=false then if
        ia2a->includes(i2.target.toString())=false then
        ia2a+=i2.target.toString() endif endif endif;
        if i2.name=self then messagefind:=true endif;
        if i2.name=str then nextmessage:=true endif;
        var
targetstate:Pseudostate=i2.target.getPseudostate(false);
        if nextmessage=false then
        {self.getrecursiveStates(messagefind, nextmessage, str,
        targetstate,false, count);} endif;

    }endif;
}
} endif;
}
}

```

```

helper String::getrecursiveStates(messagefind:Boolean, nextmessage:Boolean,
str:String, state:Pseudostate, iface1:Boolean, count:Integer)

```

```

{
  var help1:Boolean=messagefind;
  var help2:Boolean=nextmessage;
  if count=0 then
  {
    if infacel=true then
    {
      var interfacel:=ia1.objectsOfType(Transition);
      help1:=messagefind;
      help2:=nextmessage;
      interfacel->forEach(i1)
      {
        if i1.source=state then
        {
          if i1.name=self then { help1:=true; if ialb-
          >includes(i1.source.toString())=false then
          {ialb+=i1.source.toString(); }endif;}endif;
          if help1=false then { if ialb-
          >includes(state.toString())=false then
          ialb+=state.toString() endif;} endif;
          if i1.name=str then {help2:=true; } endif;
          if help1=true then if help2=false then {if ia1a-
          >includes(i1.target.toString())=false then
          ia1a+=i1.target.toString()endif;} endif endif;
          var targetstate:Pseudostate=
          i1.target.getPseudostate(infacel);
          if help2=false then {
            self.getrecursiveStates(help1, help2, str,
            targetstate,infacel, count);
          } endif;
        }
      }endif;
    }
  }
  else
  {
    var interface2:=ia2.objectsOfType(Transition);
    help1:=messagefind;
    help2:=nextmessage;
    interface2->forEach(i2)
    {
      if i2.source=state then
      {
        if i2.name=self then { help1:=true; if ia2b-
        >includes(i2.source.toString())=false then
        {ia2b+=i2.source.toString(); }endif;}endif;
        if help1=false then {if ia2b-
        >includes(state.toString())=false then
        ia2b+=state.toString() endif;} endif;
        if i2.name=str then {help2:=true; } endif;
        if help1=true then if help2=false then {if ia2a-
        >includes(i2.target.toString())=false then
        ia2a+=i2.target.toString()endif;} endif endif;
        var targetstate:Pseudostate=
        i2.target.getPseudostate(infacel);
        if help2=false then {
          self.getrecursiveStates(help1, help2, str,
          targetstate,infacel, count);
        } endif;
      }
    }endif;
  }
}
else
{
  if infacel=true then
  {

```

```

var interface1:=ia1.objectsOfType(Transition);
help1:=messagefind;
help2:=nextmessage;
interface1->forEach(i1)
{
    if i1.source=state then
    {
        if help1=true then if help2=false then if ia1a-
>includes(i1.target.toString())=false then
ia1a+=i1.target.toString() endif endif endif;
if i1.name=self then help1:=true endif;
if i1.name=str then help2:=true endif;
var
targetstate:Pseudostate=i1.target.getPseudostate(infacel);
if help2=false then {self.getrecursiveStates(help1,
help2, str, targetstate,infacel, count);} endif;
    }
endif;
}
}
else
{
var interface2:=ia2.objectsOfType(Transition);
help1:=messagefind;
help2:=nextmessage;
interface2->forEach(i2)
{
    log("Count >0 " + i2.source.toString());
    log(state.toString());
    if i2.source=state then
    {
        log("Hallo " +i2.name);
        if help1=true then if help2=false then if ia2a-
>includes(i2.target.toString())=false then
ia2a+=i2.target.toString() endif endif endif;
if i2.name=self then help1:=true endif;
if i2.name=str then help2:=true endif;
var
targetstate:Pseudostate=i2.target.getPseudostate(infacel);
if help2=false then {self.getrecursiveStates(help1,
help2, str, targetstate,infacel, count);} endif;
    }
endif;
}
}endif;
}
endif;
}

helper String::nextmessage():String
{
var message:String:="";
var count:=0;
samemessage->forEach(sm)
{
    if count=1 then {message:=sm;count:=count+1;} endif;
    if self=sm then count:=count+1 endif;
};
log("nextmessage:" + message);
return message;
}

helper String::getPseudoState(mod :String):String
{
var PseudoId:="";
var bool:=false;
if mod="1" then
{
var infacel:=ia1.objectsOfType(Transition);
infacel->forEach(i1)

```

```

        {
            if bool=false then if i1.name=self then
{PseudoId:=i1.target.toString();bool:=true;} endif endif;
        }
    }
    else if mod="2" then
    {
        var inface2:=ia2.objectsOfType(Transition);
        inface2->forEach(i2)
        {
            if bool=false then if i2.name=self then
{PseudoId:=i2.target.toString(); bool :=true } endif endif;
            };
        } endif endif;

    return PseudoId;
}

helper deleteDoubleStates()
{
    var state1:=pa.objectsOfType(Pseudostate);
    var state2:=pa.objectsOfType(Pseudostate);
    state1->forEach(s1)
    {
        var counter:=0;
        state2->forEach(s2)
        {
            if s1.name=s2.name then {counter:=counter+1; if counter>=2 then
pa.removeElement(s2)endif;} endif;
        }
    }
}

mapping Stereotype::StereoTypeToTransition(){
var transition:=pa.objectsOfType(Transition);
transition->forEach(t){
if self.name="Internal" and samemessage->includes(t.name) then
t.applyStereotype(self) endif;

var t1:=ia1.objectsOfType(Transition)->forEach(tr1)
{
    if t.name=tr1.name and samemessage->includes(t.name)=false then {if
tr1.getAppliedStereotypes().name->includes(self.name) then
t.applyStereotype(self) else{} endif} else{} endif;
};
var t2:=ia2.objectsOfType(Transition)->forEach(tr2)
{
    if t.name=tr2.name and samemessage->includes(t.name)=false then {if
tr2.getAppliedStereotypes().name->includes(self.name) then
t.applyStereotype(self) else{} endif} else{} endif;
};
};
}
}

helper deleteEmptyTransition()
{
    var trans:=pa.objectsOfType(Transition);
    trans->forEach(t1)
    {
        if t1.source=null or t1.target=null then {log("transition deleted:
"+t1.name);pa.removeElement(t1)} endif
    };
}

helper deleteEmptyStates()
{
    var state:=pa.objectsOfType(Pseudostate);
    state->forEach(ps1)
    {

```

```

        if ps1.emptyState() then {log("state
deleted:"+ps1.toString());pa.removeElement(ps1)} endif
    };
}

mapping Stereotype::StereoTypetoState() {
    var state := pa.objectsOfType(Pseudostate);
    state->forEach(s) {
        if self.name="Start" then if s.startstate()=true then
s.applyStereotype(self) endif endif;
        if self.name="End" then if s.endstate()=true then s.applyStereotype(self)
endif endif;
    };
}

helper Pseudostate::startstate():Boolean{
var transitions:=pa.objectsOfType(Transition);
var startstate:Boolean:=true;
transitions->forEach(t) {
if t.target=self then startstate:=false endif;}
;
return startstate;
}
helper Pseudostate::endstate():Boolean{
var transitions:=pa.objectsOfType(Transition);
var endstate:Boolean:=true;
transitions->forEach(t) {
if t.source=self then endstate:=false endif;}
;
return endstate;
}

helper getcount(ia:String):Integer
{

    var count:=0;
    if ia="ia1b" then ia1b->forEach(i) {count:=count+1;}
    else if ia="ia2b" then ia2b->forEach(i) {count:=count+1;}
    else if ia="ia1a" then ia1a->forEach(i) {count:=count+1;}
    else if ia="ia2a" then ia2a->forEach(i) {count:=count+1;} endif endif endif
endif;
return count;
}

helper getStartState(bool:Boolean): Pseudostate
{

    var state:Pseudostate=null;
    if bool=true then
        {
            ia1.objectsOfType(Pseudostate)->forEach(s)
            {
                if s.incoming->isEmpty() then {state:=s;} endif
            }
        }endif;
    if bool=false then
        {
            ia2.objectsOfType(Pseudostate)->forEach(s)
            {
                if s.incoming->isEmpty() then {state:=s;} endif
            }
        }
    endif;
return state;
}

helper Vertex::getPseudostate(bool:Boolean):Pseudostate
{

```

```

    if bool=true then
    {
        ia1.objectsOfType(Pseudostate)->forEach(s1)
        {
            if s1=self then return s1 endif;
        }
    }
    else
    {
        ia2.objectsOfType(Pseudostate)->forEach(s2)
        {
            if s2=self then return s2 endif;
        }
    }
    endif;
    return null;
}

helper checkdoublemessages()
{
    var helpermessage:List(String);
    samemessage->forEach(sm1)
    {
        samemessage->forEach(sm2)
        {
            if sm1=sm2 then
            {
                if helpermessage->includes(sm2)=false then
                {helpermessage+=sm2;}endif;
            }endif;
        }
    };
    samemessage:=helpermessage;
}

helper removeunreachableStates(s:Vertex, transition:Transition)
{
    pa.objectsOfType(Transition)->forEach(t)
    {
        if t.source=s then if t!=transition
        then {
            removeunreachableStates(t.target, t); removeStates+=t.target;
            log("unreachable state removed");
        } endif endif;
    }
}

helper Vertex::countoutgoingtransition(): Boolean
{
    var bool:=false;
    var counter:=0;
    pa.objectsOfType(Transition)->forEach(t)
    {
        if t.source=self then counter:=counter+1 endif;
    };
    if counter>1 then bool:=true endif;
    return bool
}

helper Vertex::countoutgoingtransitions(): Integer
{
    var counter:=0;
    pa.objectsOfType(Transition)->forEach(t)
    {
        if t.source=self then counter:=counter+1 endif;
    };
}

```

```

        return counter
    }
    helper deleteStates ()
    {
        removeStates->forEach(S)
        {
            pa.removeElement(S);
        }
    }
    helper Pseudostate::emptyState(): Boolean
    {
        var empty:=true;
        pa.objectsOfType(Transition)->forEach(T){
            if T.source=self or T.target=self then empty:=false endif;
        };
        return empty;
    }
}

```

Creation of refined interface automata (for refinement diagrams)

```

modeltype UML uses 'http://www.eclipse.org/uml2/5.0.0/UML';

transformation Refinement(inout FdIa:UML, in BmscIa:UML,in profile:UML);
main()
{
    log ("start transformation");
    FdIa.objectsOfType(Transition)->forEach(currentTransition)
    {
        if not ((currentTransition.hasStereotype("IAProfile::Internal"))or
        (BmscIa.objectsOfType(Transition).name-
        >includes(currentTransition.name)))
        then
        {
            FdIa.removeElement(currentTransition);
            log (currentTransition.name + " transition delted")
        }
        endif
    };

    while (deletablePartsLeft())
    {
        deleteUnconnectedStates();
        var initialStates:=getInitialStates();
        initialStates->forEach(currentState)
        {
            var outgoingTransitions:=currentState.outgoing;
            if (onlyInternalOutgoing(currentState))
            then
            {
                outgoingTransitions->forEach(currentTransition)
                {
                    FdIa.removeElement(currentTransition);
                    log (currentTransition.name + " transition
deleted")
                };
                FdIa.removeElement(currentState);
                log (currentState.name+ " state deleted");
            }
            endif
        };
        initialStates:=null;
    };

    var initialState:= getInitialState();
    initialState.applyStereotype(setStereotype("Start"));
}

```

```

    var finalState:=getFinalState();
    finalState.applyStereotype(setStereotype("End"));
    var initialState:=getInitialState();
    initialState.name:=getBmscIaInitialState().name
}

helper Transition::hasStereotype ( myString : String ) : Boolean
{
    var myStereotype : Stereotype := null;
    myStereotype := self.getAppliedStereotype( myString );
    return if ( self.isStereotypeApplied(myStereotype) ) then true else false endif;
}

helper getInitialStates():Set(Pseudostate)
{
    var initial:=true;
    var initialStates:Set(Pseudostate);
    FdIa.objectsOfType(Pseudostate)->forEach(currentState)
    {
        FdIa.objectsOfType(Transition)->forEach(currentTransition)
        {
            if (currentTransition.target=currentState)
            then
            {
                initial:=false;
            }
            endif
        };
        if initial=true
        then
        {
            initialStates+=currentState;
            log (currentState.name+ " is initial state")
        }
        endif;
        initial:=true;
    };
    return initialStates;
}

helper onlyInternalOutgoing(myState:Pseudostate):Boolean
{
    var returnValue:=true;
    myState.outgoing->forEach(currentTransition)
    {
        if currentTransition.hasStereotype("IAProfile::Input") or
        currentTransition.hasStereotype("IAProfile::Output")
        then
        {
            returnValue:=false;
            break;
        }
        endif
    };
    return returnValue;
}

helper deletablePartsLeft():Boolean
{
    var deletable:=false;
    if (getInitialStates()->size()>1)
    then deletable:=true
    endif;
    log ("internal: "+ (onlyInternalOutgoing(getInitialState())).toString() );
    log ("size: " + getInitialStates()->size().toString());
    if getInitialStates()->size()==1 and (onlyInternalOutgoing(getInitialState()))
    then
    {
        deletable:=true
    }
}

```

```

    }
    endif;
    log(deletable.toString());
    return deletable
}
helper getInitialState():Pseudostate
{
    var allMyStatesIAL:Set(Pseudostate);
    var allMyTransitionsIAL:=FdIa.objectsOfType(Transition);
    log ("search inital");

    allMyStatesIAL:=FdIa.objectsOfType(Pseudostate);
    allMyStatesIAL->forEach(currentState)
    {
        var initial:=true;
        allMyTransitionsIAL->forEach(currentTransition)
        {
            if currentTransition.target=currentState
            then initial:=false
            endif
        };
        if initial=true then {log ("initial state found"); return
currentState; break} endif
    };

    return null;
}

helper noOutgoing(myState:Pseudostate):Boolean
{
    var returnValue:=true;
    FdIa.objectsOfType(Transition)->forEach(currentTransition)
    {
        if currentTransition.source=myState
        then returnValue:=false
        endif
    };

    return returnValue;
}

helper deleteUnconnectedStates()
{
    FdIa.objectsOfType(Pseudostate)->forEach(currentState)
    {
        if (FdIa.objectsOfType(Transition).source->excludes(currentState) and
FdIa.objectsOfType(Transition).target->excludes(currentState))
        then FdIa.removeElement(currentState)
        endif
    }
}

helper getFinalState():Pseudostate
{
    var myState:Pseudostate;
    var allMyStatesIAL:Set(Pseudostate);
    allMyStatesIAL:=FdIa.objectsOfType(Pseudostate);
    allMyStatesIAL->forEach(currentState)
    {
        if currentState.outgoing->isEmpty()
        then myState:=currentState
        endif
    };

    return myState;
}

```

```

helper setStereotype (myString:String) :Stereotype
{
    var stereotypes:=profile.objectsOfType (Stereotype);
    stereotypes->forEach (currentStereotype)
    {
        if (myString=currentStereotype.name)
        then
        {
            return currentStereotype;
        }
        endif
    };

    return null
}

helper getBmscIaInitalState () :Pseudostate
{
    var allMyStatesIAL:Set (Pseudostate);
    var allMyTransitionsIAL:=BmscIa.objectsOfType (Transition);
    log ("search inital");

    allMyStatesIAL:=BmscIa.objectsOfType (Pseudostate);
    allMyStatesIAL->forEach (currentState)
    {
        var initial:=true;
        allMyTransitionsIAL->forEach (currentTransition)
        {
            if currentTransition.target=currentState
            then initial:=false
            endif
        }
        if initial=true then {log ("initial state found"); return
currentState; break} endif
    };

    return null;
}

```

Checking for valid refinement relations

```

modeltype UML uses 'http://www.eclipse.org/uml2/5.0.0/UML';

transformation Refineable (inout iaRefined:UML, in ia:UML, in profile:UML);
main ()
{
    var iaTransitionNames:Sequence (String);
    var iaRefinedTransitionNames:Sequence (String);
    var currentState:=getInitialStateIa ();

    while (currentState.outgoing->notEmpty ())
    {
        iaTransitionNames+=getOutgoingTransition (currentState).name;
        currentState:=getNextState (currentState);
    };
    currentState:=getInitialStateIaRefined ();
    while (currentState.outgoing->notEmpty ())
    {
        if not
(getOutgoingTransition (currentState).hasStereotype ("IAProfile::Internal"))
        then
iaRefinedTransitionNames+=getOutgoingTransition (currentState).name
        endif;
        currentState:=getNextState (currentState);
    };
}

```

```

    if (iaTransitionNames=iaRefinedTransitionNames)
    then log("Refinement Automaton")
    else {log("Unrefinable Automaton"); deleteAll() }
    endif
}

helper getInitialStateIa():Pseudostate
{
    var initialState:Pseudostate;
    ia.objectsOfType(Pseudostate)->forEach(currentState)
    {
        if currentState.incoming->isEmpty()
        then initialState:=currentState
        endif
    };
    return initialState;
}

helper getInitialStateIaRefined():Pseudostate
{
    var initialState:Pseudostate;
    iaRefined.objectsOfType(Pseudostate)->forEach(currentState)
    {
        if currentState.incoming->isEmpty()
        then initialState:=currentState
        endif
    };
    return initialState;
}

helper getOutgoingTransition(myState:Pseudostate):Transition
{
    var Transitions:=ia.objectsOfType(Transition);
    Transitions+=iaRefined.objectsOfType(Transition);
    Transitions->forEach (currentTransition)
    {
        if (myState=currentTransition.source)
        then return currentTransition
        endif
    }
}

helper getNextState(myState:Pseudostate):Pseudostate
{
    var Transitions:=ia.objectsOfType(Transition);
    Transitions+=iaRefined.objectsOfType(Transition);
    var nextTransition:Transition;
    Transitions->forEach (currentTransition)
    {
        if (myState=currentTransition.source)
        then nextTransition:=currentTransition
        endif
    };
    var States:=ia.objectsOfType(Pseudostate);
    States+=iaRefined.objectsOfType(Pseudostate);
    States->forEach(currentState)
    {
        if (currentState.incoming->includes(nextTransition))
        then return currentState
        endif
    }
}

helper Transition::hasStereotype ( myString : String ) : Boolean
{
    var myStereotype : Stereotype := null;
    myStereotype := self.getAppliedStereotype( myString );
    return if ( self.isStereotypeApplied(myStereotype) ) then true else false endif;
}

```

```

helper finalStateIA(myState:Pseudostate):Boolean
{
    var final:=true;
    ia.objectsOfType(Transition)->forEach(currentTransition)
    {
        if (myState.outgoing->includes(currentTransition))
            then final:=false
            endif
    };
    return final;
}

helper deleteAll()
{
    iaRefined.objectsOfType(Transition)->forEach(currentTransiton)
    {
        iaRefined.removeElement(currentTransiton)
    };
    iaRefined.objectsOfType(Pseudostate)->forEach(currentState)
    {
        iaRefined.removeElement(currentState)
    }
}

```

Merging of interface automata

```

modeltype UML uses "http://www.eclipse.org/uml2/5.0.0/UML";

transformation mergeIAs(in ia1:UML,in ia2:UML, profile:UML, out iaMerge: UML);

property model : UML::Model = null;

main()
{
    model := object Model { name :='model' };
    model.applyProfile(profile.objectsOfType(Profile)![name='IAProfile']);
    model.packageElement +=map CreateStateMachine();
    profile.objectsOfType(Stereotype) ->map StereotypetoState();
    profile.objectsOfType(Stereotype) ->map StereotypetoTransition();

    ia1.objectsOfType(Pseudostate)-
>forEach(currentState){currentState.getNameofState()};
    ia2.objectsOfType(Pseudostate)-
>forEach(currentState){currentState.getNameofState()};
}

mapping CreateStateMachine():StateMachine
{
    name:"StateMachine";
    region:=map regiontoStateMachine();
}

mapping regiontoStateMachine():Region
{
    name:"Region1";
    subvertex+=ia1.objectsOfType(Pseudostate)-> map StatetoRegion();
    transition+=ia1.objectsOfType(Transition)-> map TransitiontoRegion();
    subvertex+=ia2.objectsOfType(Pseudostate)-> map StatetoRegion();
    transition+=ia2.objectsOfType(Transition)-> map TransitiontoRegion();
}

mapping Pseudostate::StatetoRegion():Pseudostate
{
    name:=self.toString();
    kind:=PseudostateKind::junction;
}

```

```

}

mapping Transition::TransitiontoRegion():Transition
{
    name:=self.name;
    source:=findState(self.source.toString());
    target:=findState(self.target.toString());
}

helper findState(str:String):Pseudostate
{
    var state:Pseudostate=null;
    var allstates:= iaMerge.objectsOfType(Pseudostate);
    allstates->forEach(currentState)
    {
        if currentState.name==str then state:=currentState endif;
    };
    return state;
}

helper Pseudostate::getNameofState()
{
    var states:=iaMerge.objectsOfType(Pseudostate);
    states->forEach(currentState)
    {
        if self.toString()==currentState.name then currentState.name:=self.name
endif;
    }
}

mapping Stereotype::StereotypetoState() {
    var state := iaMerge.objectsOfType(Pseudostate);
    state->forEach(s)
    {
        if self.name="Start" then if s.startstate()==true then
s.applyStereotype(self) endif endif;
        if self.name="End" then if s.endstate()==true then
s.applyStereotype(self) endif endif;
    };
}

mapping Stereotype::StereotypetoTransition()
{
    var transition:=iaMerge.objectsOfType(Transition);
    transition->forEach(t) {
        if self.name="Input" then if t.stereotyped()=="Input" then
t.applyStereotype(self) endif endif;
        if self.name="Output" then if t.stereotyped()=="Output" then
t.applyStereotype(self) endif endif;
        if self.name="Internal" then if t.stereotyped()=="Internal" then
t.applyStereotype(self) endif endif;
    }
}

helper Pseudostate::startstate():Boolean{
var transitions:=iaMerge.objectsOfType(Transition);
var startstate:Boolean:=true;
transitions->forEach(t) {
if t.target==self then startstate:=false endif;}
;
return startstate;
}

helper Pseudostate::endstate():Boolean{
var transitions:=iaMerge.objectsOfType(Transition);
var endstate:Boolean:=true;
transitions->forEach(t) {
if t.source==self then endstate:=false endif;}
}

```

```

;
return endstate;
}

helper Transition::stereotyped():String
{
    var StereotypeName:="";
    ia1.objectsOfType(Transition)->forEach(currentTransition)
    {
        if self.name =currentTransition.name then
            if self.source.name= currentTransition.source.toString() then
                if self.target.name= currentTransition.target.toString()
then
                    {
                        currentTransition.getAppliedStereotypes()-
>forEach(stereo)
                            {
                                log(currentTransition.name+ " is Stereotyped
by "+stereo.name);
                                StereotypeName:=stereo.name
                            };
                        }
                    endif
                endif
            endif;
        };
        ia2.objectsOfType(Transition)->forEach(currentTransition)
        {
            if self.name =currentTransition.name then
                if self.source.name= currentTransition.source.toString() then
                    if self.target.name= currentTransition.target.toString()
then
                        {
                            currentTransition.getAppliedStereotypes()-
>forEach(stereo)
                                {
                                    log(currentTransition.name+ " is Stereotyped
by "+stereo.name);
                                    StereotypeName:=stereo.name
                                };
                            }
                        endif
                    endif
                endif;
            };
            return StereotypeName;
        }
    }
}

```

Creation of intermediate interface automata for unspecified diagrams

```

modeltype UML uses 'http://www.eclipse.org/uml2/5.0.0/UML';

transformation CreateUnspecifiedAutomata(inout FdIa:UML, in BmscIas:UML,in
profile:UML);

main()
{
    var allBmscIasTransitions:=BmscIas.objectsOfType(Transition);
    var allFdIaTransitions:=FdIa.objectsOfType(Transition);
    var allBmscIasTransitionsNames:Set(String);
    allBmscIasTransitions->forEach(currentTransiton)
    {
        allBmscIasTransitionsNames+=currentTransiton.name;
    };
    allFdIaTransitions->forEach(currentTransition)
    {
        if (allBmscIasTransitionsNames->includes(currentTransition.name))
then FdIa.removeElement(currentTransition)

```

```

        endif
    };

    deleteStates();

    var initialStates:=getInitialStates();
    var counter:=1;
    initialStates->forEach(currentState)
    {
        currentState.name="FD"+counter.toString();
        counter:=counter+1;--}

    };

    initialStates:= getInitialStates();
    initialStates->forEach(currentState)
    {
        currentState.applyStereotype(setStereotype("Start"));
    };

    var finalStates:=getFinalStates();
    finalStates->forEach(currentState)
    {
        currentState.applyStereotype(setStereotype("End"));
    }
}

helper deleteStates()
{
    var states:=FdIa.objectsOfType(Pseudostate);
    var transitions:=FdIa.objectsOfType(Transition);
    states->forEach(currentState)
    {
        var deleteable:=true;
        transitions->forEach(currentTransition)
        {
            if currentTransition.source=currentState or
currentTransition.target=currentState
            then deleteable:=false endif;
        };
        if deleteable=true then FdIa.removeElement(currentState) endif;
    }
}

helper getInitialStates():Set(Pseudostate)
{
    log("gis");
    var initial:=true;
    var initialStates:Set(Pseudostate);
    FdIa.objectsOfType(Pseudostate)->forEach(currentState)
    {
        FdIa.objectsOfType(Transition)->forEach(currentTransition)
        {
            if (currentTransition.target=currentState)
            then
            {
                initial:=false;
            }
            endif
        };
        if initial=true
        then
        {
            initialStates+=currentState;
            log(currentState.name+ " is initial state found")
        }
        endif;
        initial:=true;
    };
    return initialStates;
}

```

```

}

helper setStereotype(myString:String):Stereotype
{
    var stereotypes:=profile.objectsOfType(Stereotype);
    stereotypes->forEach(currentStereotype)
    {
        if (myString=currentStereotype.name)
        then
        {
            return currentStereotype;
        }
        endif
    };

    return null
}

helper getFinalStates():Set(Pseudostate)
{
    log ("gis");
    var initial:=true;
    var initialStates:Set(Pseudostate);
    FdIa.objectsOfType(Pseudostate)->forEach(currentState)
    {
        FdIa.objectsOfType(Transition)->forEach(currentTransition)
        {
            if (currentTransition.source=currentState)
            then
            {
                initial:=false;
            }
            endif
        };
        if initial=true
        then
        {
            initialStates+=currentState;
            log (currentState.name+ " is initial state found")
        }
        endif;
        initial:=true;
    };
    return initialStates;
}

```

Creation of an hMSC for the Unspecified Diagrams

```

modeltype UML uses 'http://www.eclipse.org/uml2/5.0.0/UML';

transformation createHmscPart1(inout FdIa:UML, in BmscIas:UML );

main()
{
    while (bmscAutomataLeft())
    {
        var initialStateOfNextBmscAutomaton:=getInitialStateFromNextBmscAutomaton();
        var sameInitialStateInFdAutomaton:=findSameInitialStateInFdAutomaton
        (initialStateOfNextBmscAutomaton);
        var finalStateOfNextBmscAutomaton
        :=getFinalStateFromNextBmscAutomaton(initialStateOfNextBmscAutomaton);
        var
        sameFinalStateInFdAutomaton:=findSameFinalStateInFdAutomaton(finalStateOfNextBmscAu
        tomaton);
        var mscReferenceName:=initialStateOfNextBmscAutomaton.name;
        map createMscReference(mscReferenceName);
    }
}

```

```

        map createIncomingFlowLine(mscReferenceName, sameInitialStateInFdAutomaton);
        map createOutgoingFlowLine(mscReferenceName, sameFinalStateInFdAutomaton);
        deleteBmscAutomaton(initialStateOfNextBmscAutomaton, finalStateOfNextBmscAutomaton);
    }
}

mapping createMscReference(myName:String):State
{
    name:=myName;
    log("MSC reference created")
}

mapping createIncomingFlowLine(mscName:String,myState:Pseudostate):Transition
{
    source:=myState;
    target:=getMscReference(mscName);
    log("Flow Line from: "+source.toString() + " to: "+target.toString());
}

mapping createOutgoingFlowLine(mscName:String,myState:Pseudostate):Transition
{
    source:=getMscReference(mscName);
    target:=myState;
    log("Flow Line from: "+source.toString() + " to: "+target.toString());
}

helper bmscAutomataLeft():Boolean
{
    var automataLeft:=true;
    if(BmscIas.objectsOfType(Pseudostate)->isEmpty())
        automataLeft:=false
    endif;
    log("bMSC automata left" +automataLeft.toString());
    return automataLeft;
}

helper getInitialStateFromNextBmscAutomaton():Pseudostate
{
    BmscIas.objectsOfType(Pseudostate)->forEach(currentState)
    {
        if(currentState.incoming->isEmpty())
            then
                {
                    log("next bMSC automaton found");
                    return currentState
                }
            endif;
    }
}

helper getFinalStateFromNextBmscAutomaton(initialState:Pseudostate):Pseudostate
{
    var currentState:=initialState;
    while(not(currentState.outgoing->isEmpty()))
    {
        currentState:=getNextState(currentState);
    };
    log("final state of bMSC automaton found");
    return currentState;
}

helper findSameInitialStateInFdAutomaton(bmscInitialState:Pseudostate):Pseudostate
{
    var sameState:Pseudostate;
    var outgoingTransitionName:=getNameOfOutgoingTransition(bmscInitialState);
    FdIa.objectsOfType(Pseudostate)->forEach(currentState)
    {
        if(currentState.outgoing.name->includes(outgoingTransitionName))
            then

```

```

        {
            log("same state in FD automaton found");
            sameState:=currentState
        }
        endif;
};

return sameState;
}
helper findSameFinalStateInFdAutomaton (bmscFinalState:Pseudostate) :Pseudostate
{
    var sameState:Pseudostate;
    var incomingTransitionName:=getNameOfIncomingTransition (bmscFinalState);
    FdIa.objectsOfType (Pseudostate) ->forEach (currentState)
    {
        if (currentState.incoming.name->includes (incomingTransitionName))
        then sameState:=currentState
        endif;
    };
    log ("same final state in FD automaton found");

    return sameState;
}
helper getMscReference (myName:String) :State
{
    FdIa.objectsOfType (State) ->forEach (currentState)
    {
        if currentState.name=myName
        then return currentState
        endif;
    }
}
helper getNamesOfOutgoingTransitions (myState:Pseudostate) :Set (String)
{
    var transitionNames:Set (String);
    myState.outgoing->forEach (currentTransition)
    {
        transitionNames+=currentTransition.name;
    };
    return transitionNames;
}
helper getNamesOfIncomingTransitions (myState:Pseudostate) :Set (String)
{
    var transitionNames:Set (String);
    myState.incoming->forEach (currentTransition)
    {
        transitionNames+=currentTransition.name;
    };
    return transitionNames;
}
helper getTransitions (myTransitionsNames:Set (String)) :Set (Transition)
{
    return transition;
}
helper deleteBmscAutomaton (initialState:Pseudostate, finalState:Pseudostate)
{
    var currentState:=initialState;
    var statesLeft:Set (Pseudostate);
    statesLeft+=currentState;
    while (not (statesLeft->isEmpty()))
    {
        var outgoingTransitions:=getOutgoingTransitions (currentState);
        var
outgoingTransitionNames:=getNamesOfOutgoingTransitions (currentState);
        FdIa.objectsOfType (Transition) ->forEach (currentTransition)
        {
            if outgoingTransitionNames->includes (currentTransition.name)
            then
            {
                FdIa.removeElement (currentTransition);
            }
        }
    }
}

```

```

                log ("transition: "+ currentTransition.toString()+" in FD
deleted");
            }
            endif;
        };

statesLeft+=getNextStates (outgoingTransitions);
BmscIas.objectsOfType(Transition)->forEach (currentTransition)
{
    if outgoingTransitions->includes (currentTransition)
    then
    {
        BmscIas.removeElement (currentTransition);
        log (currentTransition.name+" deleted in BR");
    }
    endif;
};
BmscIas.removeElement (currentState);
log (currentState.name+" delted in BR");
log (statesLeft->size().toString()+" states left");
var newStatesLeft:Set (Pseudostate);
statesLeft->forEach (currentStateInLoop)
{
    if (currentStateInLoop<>currentState)
    then newStatesLeft+=currentStateInLoop
    endif;
};
statesLeft:=newStatesLeft;
if (statesLeft->notEmpty())
then currentState:=getNextElement (statesLeft)
endif;

};
BmscIas.removeElement (currentState);

}
helper getNextState (myState:Pseudostate):Pseudostate
{
    var nextState:Pseudostate;
    var outgoingTransition:=getOneTransition (myState.outgoing);
    nextState:=findNextState (outgoingTransition);
    log (outgoingTransition.name + "ends in state: "+nextState.name);
    return nextState;
}
helper getNameOfOutgoingTransition (bmscInitialState:Pseudostate):String
{
    var transitionName:String;
    bmscInitialState.outgoing->forEach (currentTransition)
    {
        transitionName:=currentTransition.name;
    };
    return transitionName;
}
helper getNameOfIncomingTransition (bmscFinalState:Pseudostate):String
{
    var transitionName:String;
    bmscFinalState.incoming->forEach (currentTransition)
    {
        transitionName:=currentTransition.name;
    };
    return transitionName;
}
helper finalState (myState:Pseudostate):Boolean
{
    var finalState:=false;
    BmscIas.objectsOfType(Transition)->forEach (currentTransition)
    {
        if currentTransition.source=myState

```

```

        then finalState:=false
        else
        {
            return true;
            break;
        }
        endif;
    };
    log ("final state reached: "+finalState.toString());
    return finalState;
}
helper getOutgoingTransitions (myState:Pseudostate) :Set(Transition)
{
    var outgoingTransitions:Set(Transition);
    outgoingTransitions:=myState.outgoing;
    log (outgoingTransitions->size().toString()+" outgoing Transitions found. ");
    return outgoingTransitions;
}
helper getNextStates (myTransitions:Set(Transition)) :Set(Pseudostate)
{
    var nextStates:Set(Pseudostate);
    BmscIas.objectsOfType(Pseudostate)->forEach(currentState)
    {
        myTransitions->forEach(currentTransition)
        {
            if currentState.incoming->includes(currentTransition)
            then nextStates+=currentState
            endif
        }
    };
    log (nextStates->size().toString()+" next states found");

    return nextStates;
}
helper getNextElement (states:Set(Pseudostate)) :Pseudostate
{
    var nextState:Pseudostate;
    states->forEach(currentState)
    {
        nextState:=currentState;
    };
    return nextState;
}
helper getOneTransition (myTransitions:Set(Transition)) :Transition
{
    var myTransition:Transition;
    myTransitions->forEach(currentTransition)
    {
        myTransition:=currentTransition;
    };
    return myTransition;
}
helper findNextState (myTransition:Transition) :Pseudostate
{
    var myState:Pseudostate;
    var allStates:=BmscIas.objectsOfType(Pseudostate);
    allStates->forEach(currentState)
    {
        if currentState=myTransition.target
        then myState:= currentState
        endif
    };
    return myState;
}
modeltype UML uses 'http://www.eclipse.org/uml2/5.0.0/UML';

```

```

transformation createHmscPart2 (in stateDiagram:UML, out hMSC:UML);

main ()

{
    stateDiagram.objects() [StateMachine]-> map createActivity();
}
mapping StateMachine::createActivity():Activity
{
    stateDiagram.objects() [State]->map createMscReferences();
    stateDiagram.objectsOfType(Pseudostate)->forEach(currentConnectionPoint)
    {
        var sources:Bag(Vertex);
        sources:=currentConnectionPoint.incoming.source;
        var targets:Bag(Vertex);
        targets:=currentConnectionPoint.outgoing.target;

        sources->forEach(currentSource)
        {
            targets->forEach(currentTarget)
            {
                map createControlFlow(currentSource.name,
currentTarget.name);
            }
        }
    };

var namesOfAllInitialNodes:=getNamesOfAllInitialNodes();
map createMscReferenceByName("Initial Node");
namesOfAllInitialNodes->forEach(currentNode)
{
    map createControlFlow("Initial Node", currentNode)
};

var namesOfAllFinalNodes:=getNamesOfAllFinalNodes();
map createMscReferenceByName("Final Node");
namesOfAllFinalNodes->forEach(currentNode)
{
    map createControlFlow(currentNode, "Final Node")
};
}

mapping State::createMscReferences():OpaqueAction
{
    name:=self.name;
}
mapping createControlFlow(mySource:String,myTarget:String):ControlFlow
{
    source:=getMscReference(mySource);
    target:=getMscReference(myTarget);
}

mapping createMscReferenceByName(myName:String):OpaqueAction
{
    name:=myName;
}

helper getMscReference(mySource:String):OpaqueAction
{
    hMSC.objectsOfType(OpaqueAction)->forEach(currentMscReference)
    {
        if currentMscReference.name==mySource
        then return currentMscReference
        endif;
    }
}

helper getNamesOfAllInitialNodes():Set(String)
{

```

```

    var names:Set(String);
    hMSC.objectsOfType(OpaqueAction)->forEach(currentMscReference)
    {
        if (currentMscReference.incoming->isEmpty())
            then names+=currentMscReference.name
            endif
    };
    return names;
}

helper getNamesOfAllFinalNodes():Set(String)
{
    var names:Set(String);
    hMSC.objectsOfType(OpaqueAction)->forEach(currentMscReference)
    {
        if (currentMscReference.outgoing->isEmpty())
            then names+=currentMscReference.name
            endif
    };
    return names;
}

```

Merging of hMSCs

```

modeltype UML uses 'http://www.eclipse.org/uml2/5.0.0/UML';

transformation HmscMerge (inout BrHmsc:UML, in FdHmsc:UML, in profile:UML);

main()
{
    log ('-- Start transformation');

    BrHmsc.objectsOfType(OpaqueAction)->forEach(currentNode)
    {
        if(not (FdHmsc.objectsOfType(OpaqueAction).name-
>includes(currentNode.name)))
            then
                {
                    log("unrefinable node: " + currentNode.name);
                    currentNode.applyStereotype(setStereotype("BR_Node"))
                }
            endif
    };

    BrHmsc.objectsOfType(ControlFlow)->forEach(currentEdge)
    {
        if (not(edgeExistsInFdHmsc(currentEdge)))
            then
                {
                    log("unrefinable edge");
                    currentEdge.applyStereotype(setStereotype("BR"))
                }
            endif
    };

    FdHmsc.objectsOfType(OpaqueAction)->forEach(currentActivity)
    {
        if (not(BrHmsc.objectsOfType(OpaqueAction).name-
>includes(currentActivity.name)))
            then map addNode(currentActivity)
            endif;
    };

    FdHmsc.objectsOfType(ControlFlow)->forEach(currentEdge)
    {

```

```

        if (not(edgeExistsInBrHmsc(currentEdge)))
        then map addEdge(currentEdge)
        endif;
};

log ('-- Transformtion finished');
}

mapping addNode(myNode:OpaqueAction):OpaqueAction
{
    name:=myNode.name;
    log ("unspecified node");
    myNode.applyStereotype(setStereotype("FD_Node"))
}

mapping addEdge(myEdge:ControlFlow):ControlFlow
{
    source:=getSource(myEdge);
    target:=getTarget(myEdge);
    log ("unspecified edge");
    myEdge.applyStereotype(setStereotype("FD"))
}

helper edgeExistsInBrHmsc(myEdge:ControlFlow):Boolean
{
    var exists:=false;
    var sameSource:Set(ControlFlow);
    BrHmsc.objectsOfType(ControlFlow)->forEach(currentControlFlow)
    {
        if (currentControlFlow.source.name=myEdge.source.name)
        then
        {
            sameSource+=currentControlFlow;
            log ("sameSource")
        }
        endif;
    };
    sameSource->forEach(currentControlFlow)
    {
        if (currentControlFlow.target.name=myEdge.target.name)
        then exists:=true
        endif
    };

    return exists;
}

helper edgeExistsInFdHmsc(myEdge:ControlFlow):Boolean
{
    var exists:=false;
    var sameSource:Set(ControlFlow);
    FdHmsc.objectsOfType(ControlFlow)->forEach(currentControlFlow)
    {
        if (currentControlFlow.source.name=myEdge.source.name)
        then
        {
            sameSource+=currentControlFlow;
            log ("sameSource")
        }
        endif;
    };
    sameSource->forEach(currentControlFlow)
    {
        if (currentControlFlow.target.name=myEdge.target.name)
        then exists:=true
        endif
    };
};

```

```

        return exists;
    }

    helper getSource(myEdge:ControlFlow):OpaqueAction
    {
        var source:OpaqueAction;
        BrHmsc.objectsOfType(OpaqueAction)->forEach(currentNode)
        {
            if currentNode.name=myEdge.source.name
            then source:=currentNode
            endif
        };
        return source;
    }

    helper getTarget(myEdge:ControlFlow):OpaqueAction
    {
        var target:OpaqueAction;
        BrHmsc.objectsOfType(OpaqueAction)->forEach(currentNode)
        {
            if currentNode.name=myEdge.target.name
            then target:=currentNode
            endif
        };
        return target;
    }

    helper setStereotype(myString:String):Stereotype
    {
        var stereotypes:=profile.objectsOfType(Stereotype);
        stereotypes->forEach(currentStereotype)
        {
            if (myString=currentStereotype.name)
            then
            {
                return currentStereotype;
            }
            endif
        };

        return null
    }

```

Graphical creation of an hMSC with Papyrus

```

modeltype NOTATION uses 'http://www.eclipse.org/gmf/runtime/1.0.2/notation';
modeltype ECORE uses "http://www.eclipse.org/emf/2002/Ecore";
modeltype STYLE uses 'http://www.eclipse.org/papyrus/infra/viewpoints/policy/style';
modeltype UML uses 'http://www.eclipse.org/uml2/5.0.0/UML';

transformation graficforhmsc( in inmodel: UML, out notation:NOTATION, out di:STYLE);
property messages : Set ( MessageOccurrenceSpecification ) = Set {};
property actions : Set ( OpaqueAction ) = Set {};
property controls : Set ( ControlFlow ) = Set{};
property lifelines : Set ( Lifeline ) = Set {};
property model : UML::Model = null;
property wert1: Integer=20;
property wert2: Integer=20;
property counter: Integer=1;

main() {
    log ('--Start Transformation');

    inmodel.objectsOfType(Activity)->map ActivitytoDiagram();
    log ('--Processed');
}
mapping Activity::ActivitytoDiagram():NOTATION::Diagram
{
    type:= 'PapyrusUMLActivityDiagram';
    name:= 'FunctionNet';
}

```

```

measurementUnit:= MeasurementUnit::Pixel;

var shape:notation::Shape:= object Shape{type:="2001"};
var layout:notation::LayoutConstraint:=object Bounds{};
shape.element:= self.oclAsType(ecore::EObject);
shape.layoutConstraint:=layout;
children+=shape;
var decnode1:notation::Node:= object DecorationNode{type:="5001"};
shape.children+=decnode1;

var decnode2:notation::Node:= object DecorationNode{type:="7001"};
var style1:notation::Style:= object SortingStyle{};
var style2:notation::Style:= object FilteringStyle{};
var layout1:notation::LayoutConstraint:= object Bounds{};
decnode2.styles+=style1;decnode2.styles+=style2; decnode2.layoutConstraint:=layout1;
shape.children+=decnode2;

var decnode3:notation::Node:= object DecorationNode{type:="7002"};
var style3:notation::Style:= object SortingStyle{};
var style4:notation::Style:= object FilteringStyle{};
var layout2:notation::LayoutConstraint:= object Bounds{};
decnode3.styles+=style3;decnode3.styles+=style4; decnode3.layoutConstraint:=layout2;
shape.children+=decnode3;

var decnode4:notation::Node:= object DecorationNode{type:="7003"};
var style5:notation::Style:= object SortingStyle{};
var style6:notation::Style:= object FilteringStyle{};
var layout3:notation::LayoutConstraint:= object Bounds{};
decnode4.styles+=style5;decnode4.styles+=style6; decnode4.layoutConstraint:=layout3;
shape.children+=decnode4;

inmodel.objectsOfType(OpaqueAction)-> map OpaquetoShape();

var decnode:notation::Node:= object DecorationNode{type:="7004"};
shape.children+=decnode;
var bound:notation::LayoutConstraint := object Bounds{};

decnode.layoutConstraint:=bound;
decnode.children+=inmodel.objectsOfType(OpaqueAction)-> map OpaquetoShape();
inmodel.objectsOfType(ControlFlow)-> map FlowtoEdge();

var stringstyle:NOTATION::Style:=object
StringValueStyle{name:="diagram_compatibility_version"; stringValue:="1.0.0"};
var diastyle:NOTATION::Style:=object DiagramStyle{};
var papyrusstyle:NOTATION::Style:=object STYLE::PapyrusViewStyle {
owner:=model.oclAsType(ecore::EObject)};
styles+=stringstyle;
styles+= diastyle;
styles+=papyrusstyle;
element:=self.oclAsType(ecore::EObject);
var connectors:= notation.objectsOfType(NOTATION::Connector);
connectors-> forEach(c)
{
    edges+=c;
};
}
mapping OpaqueAction::OpaquetoShape(): NOTATION::Shape
{
    type:="3007";
    var detail1:ecore::EStringToStringMapEntry:= object
EStringToStringMapEntry{key:="StereotypeWithQualifiedNameList"; value:=""};
    var detail2:ecore::EStringToStringMapEntry:= object
EStringToStringMapEntry{key:="StereotypeList"; value:="FunctionNetProfile::BR_Node"};
    var detail3:ecore::EStringToStringMapEntry:= object
EStringToStringMapEntry{key:="Stereotype_Presentation_Kind"; value:="HorizontalStereo"};
    var detail4:ecore::EStringToStringMapEntry:= object
EStringToStringMapEntry{key:="PropStereoDisplay"; value:=""};
    var detail5:ecore::EStringToStringMapEntry:= object
EStringToStringMapEntry{key:="StereotypePropertyLocation"; value:="Compartment"};
    var annotate:ecore::EAnnotation:=object EAnnotation
    {
        source:="Stereotype_Annotation";
        details+=detail1;
        details+=detail2;
        details+=detail3;
        details+=detail4;
        details+=detail5
    };
};

```

```

eAnnotations:=annotate;

var decnode:notation::Node:= object DecorationNode{type:="5003"};
children+=decnode;
var style:notation::Style := object HintedDiagramLinkStyle{};
styles:=style;
element:=self.oclAsType(ecore::EObject);
var bound:notation::LayoutConstraint := object Bounds{x:=wert2; y:=wert1};

if counter.toString()=="8" then {wert1:=20; counter:=1} else wert1:=wert1+80 endif;
if wert1.toString()=="20" then wert2:=wert2+200 endif;
counter:=counter+1;
layoutConstraint:=bound;
}

mapping ControlFlow::FlowtoEdge(): NOTATION::Connector
{
var nodes:= notation.objectsOfType(Shape);
var sourceshape:NOTATION::Shape:=null;
var targetshape:NOTATION::Shape:=null;
var selfmessage:Boolean:=false;
nodes-> forEach(n)
{
if self.source.toString() = n.element.toString() then sourceshape:=n endif;
if self.target.toString()= n.element.toString() then targetshape:=n endif;
};

element:=self.oclAsType(ecore::EObject);
source:= sourceshape;
target:= targetshape;
type:="4004";
var decnode:notation::Node:= object DecorationNode{type:="6003"};
var layout:notation::LayoutConstraint:= object Location{ y:=20};
decnode.layoutConstraint:= layout;
children+=decnode;
var decnode1:notation::Node:= object DecorationNode{type:="6004"};
var layout1:notation::LayoutConstraint:= object Location{ y:=20};
decnode1.layoutConstraint:= layout1;

children+=decnode1;
var decnode2:notation::Node:= object DecorationNode{type:="6009"};
var layout2:notation::LayoutConstraint:= object Location{ y:=20};
decnode2.layoutConstraint:= layout2;
children+=decnode2;
var decnode3:notation::Node:= object DecorationNode{type:="6011"};
var layout3:notation::LayoutConstraint:= object Location{ y:=-20};
decnode3.layoutConstraint:= layout3;

children+=decnode3;
var fontstyle:notation::Style:= object FontStyle{};
styles+=fontstyle;
var bends: Bends:= object RelativeEndpoints{};

bendpoints:=bends;

var sanchor:notation::Anchor:= object IdentityAnchor{};
var tanchor:notation::Anchor:= object IdentityAnchor{};

sourceAnchor:=sanchor;
targetAnchor:=tanchor
}

```